

ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR TOWARDS ENVIRONMENT: AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW AND FUTURE AGENDA

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Abstract

The paper aims to examine the major factors responsible for Organizational Citizenship Behavior towards Environment (OCBE). This integrative review includes 153 papers from 2000 to 2022. The study discusses the evolution of OCBE. Further, the study divides the antecedents of OCBE into two level of interventions i.e., employee level interventions (Employee characteristics), and organizational level interventions (Human Resource Strategies and Leadership Styles). The impact of such interventions on OCBE is discussed. The study infers that OCBE improves overall organizational performance, hence, achieving long-term sustainability. Lastly, the study discusses the implications and future research agenda.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behavior towards Environment (OCBE), Human Resource Strategies, Employee characteristics, Leadership Styles, Organizational Performance, Integrative Review

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has always been a long-term goal for the company (Amrutha & Geetha, 2020; Malik et al., 2021; Milanesi et al. Yong et al., 2020). Caradonna (2014) argues that "sustainable" encompasses more than just "the environment" and should include attention to social stability (health, equality, democracy, and justice), as well as the interconnectivity of these areas. Every day, many businesses work to be more sustainable, and they emphasise this in their yearly sustainability reports. In this report, the firm emphasises its global corporate citizenship initiatives in relation to the important ecological, social, and governance concerns that are important to the company and shareholders, employees, consumers, and other stakeholders. For example, the announcements of Microsoft's transition to carbon neutrality, Starbucks' pledge to become "resource positive," and Dell's pledge to cut the consumption levels of its product line by 80% all came at the same time (Confino, 2014). The importance of achieving sustainability is widely realized and various initiatives are undertaken to achieve sustainable goals. Adoption of sustainable practices requires organizational-wide buy in and understanding. The key to understanding sustainability is to consider how each employee can actively support and contribute to the implementation of such strategic initiatives (Jayabalan, 2020; Lozano, 2015; van Marrewijk and Werre, 2003).

As organisations are responsible for environmental damage, they also bear duty for its preservation (Ones & Dilchert, 2012). Enterprises take action to improve their environmental

practices by promoting eco-friendly behaviour among their staff (Rizvi&Garg, 2021). This has drawn the attention of academics to environmental citizenship behavior or pro-environmental behavior of employees (Raineri&Paille, 2015; Paille&Raineri, 2016). One such concept is Organizational Citizenship Behavior towards Environment (OCBE). Initially, Daily et al. (2009) adapted the OCB framework (Organ, 1988) in order to define OCBE as "individual and discretionary social actions that are not directly acknowledged by the formal reward system and that lead to a more effective environmental management by organisations" (p. 4). Boiral and Paille (2012) developed a measure of OCBE based on this description, which consists of three components: environmental, eco-helping, and eco-civic participation. This discretionary behavior is known by a variety of terms, including pro-environment behavior (Lu, Zhang, Diao, Liu, Chen, Long & Cai, 2021; Robertson & Barling, 2013), employee green behavior (Norton, Parker, Zacher&Ashkanasy, 2015), eco-friendly behavior (Kim, Kim, Choia, Phetvaroon, 2019), OCBE (Daily, Bishop, Govindarajulu, 2009; Temminck, Mearns&Fruhen, 2015). To reduce complication, the study refers to this environmentally conscious behavior using a single word, OCBE, since all of the previously described concepts refer to the same phenomenon.

Studies on OCBE are gaining importance but yet not much attention has been given to the variables that enable this environment specific behavior of employees in both organizational and employee level contexts (Lu, Zhang, Diao, Liu, Chen, Long & Cai, 2021, MdYusop&Azreen Adam, 2021). Even though Yuriev, Boiral, Francoeur, and Paille (2018) and Lu et al. (2021) have done systematic and bibliometric studies, the integrative review still remains elusive. Further, evaluation of demographic distribution and research fields of related studies needs to be examined for evaluating the scope of interest area. Thus, the study conducts an integrative review to address these gaps by focusing on these three research questions:

RQ1: How has OCBE evolved since 2000 until 2022?

RQ2: What are the major industries and theories that contribute to OCBE's literature in the past two decades?

RQ3: What are the major employee level and organizational level interventions that help an organization embrace OCBE?

The study consists of three parts. Firstly, the study outlines the evolution stage of OCBE and its various scales (from 2000–2022). The second part will state the demographic distribution, research specific industries and theories of OCBE. Thirdly, the categorization of OCBE's antecedents under two levels of interventions i.e., organizational and individual level interventions that help in embracing OCBE and achieving environmental goals of an organization is discussed.

METHODOLOGY

Method

To give readers a more thorough grasp of the research issue, the integrative review compiles the results of earlier theoretical and empirical studies. The integrative review adapts a variety

of methodologies including experimental and non-experimental methods to provide a more inclusive meaning of OCBE (Steg&Vlek, 2009). According to Callahan (2010), an integrative literature review is a method that includes information about the sources from which the literature was extracted, the time the search was conducted, the person who conducted the search, how the literature was found, the the last count of included articles, and the inclusion criteria used to determine the final number of articles that were taken into account (Torraco, 2005).

Collection of literature

The literature search includes publications from 2000 to 2022 that were published in a variety of databases, including the Web of Science (WoS) and Google. The WoS database is used in the study because it allows for in-depth analysis of scientific or academic themes and gives access to numerous databases that include cross-disciplinary research. The inclusion of the Google Scholar search engine enhances the scope of this integrative review by extending the reach and including a variety of articles that are not covered in the WoS database. The search was conducted using the keywords, TI = {"Organizational citizenship behavio*towards environment*" OR "corporate sustainability" OR "pro-environment behavio*" OR "voluntary behavio*towards environment" OR "workplace behavio*towards sustainability" OR "environment*management practices" OR "employee green behavio*" OR "organization*environment*citizenship behavio*" OR "sustainable behavio*" and "green behavio*"}.

Selection of relevant literature

The initial search resulted in 1884 papers which were narrowed down to 756 after excluding duplicate papers, conference papers and papers not written in English. Further, 480 articles were eliminated based on their titles, abstracts, and keywords, resulting in 276 articles for full text review. Following a phased review procedure, only the papers that met the study's inclusion criteria (see below) and were deemed to be the most relevant were given further consideration, further narrowing the pool of publications (Torraco, 2005). The screening of the full text is based on the relevance of the articles by distinguishing organizational and non-organizational level studies and their applicability. The articles which focused on OCBE adoption process, theoretical building and strategies adopted for modifying employee behavior by indulging in environment friendly actions were included in the study. Articles focusing on environmental management services or management norms that are unrelated to employee specific behavior were not included. This results in 124 articles and after using backward reference searching technique, the addition of 29 articles took place. A backward reference searching involves identifying and examining the references cited in an article. A total of 153 papers were obtained. Figure 1 represents the study flow diagram of the reviewed articles (PRISMA flow diagram).

Figure 1: Study Flow Diagram

ANALYSIS

The findings of the study are categorized into two parts i.e., the evolution of OCBE and its trend from 2000 to 2022, and the effect of employee and organization level interventions in endeavouring OCBE.

The first part outlines the journey of OCBE from its evolution until 2022 and the repetitive theories used in the selected articles. It further discusses the trends observed in OCBE's research in the mentioned time frame, its scales evolved until now and industry distribution.

The second part consists of distributing antecedents of OCBE into two categories i.e., organizational and employee level interventions that have an impact on OCBE in the long run.

OCBE's Evolution and trends

The study performed a descriptive method of journal articles since 2000 in major international publications in order to examine the trends in the growth of OCBE. The figure 2 shows the upward trend in the number of publications per year since 2000. The significant growth in the number of publications after 2009 is due to the conceptual clarification of OCBE provided by Boiral (2009) and Daily et al. (2009). The development of the most well-liked included as for OCBE by Paille&Boiral (2012) and Bissing-Olson et al. can be attributed to the significant increase of publications that occurred after 2012. (2013). the increase in publication after 2017 may be due to the availability of a more inclusive and wide-applicability measurement scale developed by Robertson & Barling (2017). The slight decline in 2020 may be due to the outbreak of pandemic across the globe. A sharp rise in 2021 can be inferred as the crisis were

under control globally. Thus, the continuous increasing trend is definitely due to the wider availability of scales to measure OCBE provided by various authors and its gaining importance over the last decade. Few of the most prominent scales used are Boiral&Paille (2012), Robertson and Barling (2013, 2017), Bissing-Olson et al. (2013) and Graves et al. (2013). This proves the interest of researchers in the field of OCBE is accelerating. Still there is a need to develop a scale that captures collective measures along with individual measures of an individual's pro-environment behavior (Francoeur et al., 2019).

Figure 2: Number of publications per year

Table 1: Journal wise paper distribution

Journal	No.	Journal	No.
Sustainability	11	Academy of Management Review	2
Environment and Behavior	9	Research in Hospitality Management	2
Journal of Environmental Psychology	9	Journal of Management	1
Journal of Cleaner Production	8	Facilities	1
Journal of Sustainable Tourism	7	Journal of Management Studies	1
Journal of Business Ethics	7	Journal of Operations Management	1
Organization & Environment	6	Group & Organizational Management	1
Journal of Organizational Behavior	6	International Journal of Operations & Production Management	1
Journal of Business Research	6	Journal of supply chain management	1
Environmental Education Research	5		
Frontiers in Psychology	5		
International Journal of Consumer Studies	5		

Business Strategy and Environment	5	The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science	1
Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	4	Journal of World Business	1
Human Resource Management Review	4	Journal of Applied Social Psychology	1
Tourism Management	4	Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability	1
International Journal of Hospitality Management	3	European Association of Work and Organizational Psychology	1
The psychology of green organizations	3	Business & Society	1
Current Psychology	2	International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management	1
Journal of Environment Planning and Management	2	European Association of Work and Organizational Psychology	1
Resources, Conservation & Recycling	2	Asia-Pacific Management and Business Application	1
Human Relations	2	Leadership & Organization Development Journal	1
European Management Review	2		
Journal of Management and Operation Research	2		
Journal of Environmental Accounting and Management	2		
California Management Review	2		
Journal of Environmental Economics and Management	2		
Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research	2		

Further the table 1 shows the list of journals from where the papers were extracted for the study. It can be inferred that OCBE is widely implemented in variety of fields representing organizational psychology, marketing, strategic management, sustainable production and consumption, economics, management and information systems. This list illustrates the interdisciplinary characteristics of OCBE as an area of study since 2000. Most of the journals focus on either sustainable production or consumption and environmental management issues in different industries.

Figure 3: Industry wise distribution of papers

Figure 3 represents the distribution of papers published with respect to the industries mentioned. The maximum number of papers has been studied in the service sector (46%) followed by the manufacturing sector (41%) and multiple industries (11%). The service sector includes various industries namely, education, banking, tourism and hospitality, and healthcare industry. The manufacturing sector includes various industries namely, textiles and clothing, fertilizers, pesticides and other chemicals, oil and gas, pharmaceuticals, FMCG and consumer goods, and construction and housing. The multiple industry also covers significant papers which signifies the popularity of cross-industries in OCBE's research. The most popular industries are observed to be Tourism and hospitality, followed by education and then by chemical producing industries. The popularity of OCBE in these industries can be due to high wastage and disposal issues that disturb the environmental footprints, like chemical manufacturing industry which produces harmful residuals and wastes, or tourism and hospitality industry which has huge disposal issues due to daily wastage. The largest number of publications are in environmental related journals with the above-mentioned industries as seen in Table 1. Further, the scope of OCBE in industries like IT, oil and gas and FMCG needs attention as these industries have high environmental footprints and waste disposal issues.

The few most repetitive theories that are extracted from literature are mentioned in table 2. The theories focus on individual behavior and its surroundings, so it is important to examine the antecedents from an employee and organizational perspective. To adopt this sustainable practise, organizations must take action by way of interventions (Yuriev, Dahmen, Paille, Boiral, &Guillaumie, 2020). For this purpose, the study categorized such antecedents under two broad categories i.e., employee level interventions and organizational level interventions.

Table 2: Most repetitive theories adopted in the papers reviewed

Theory	Definition
Theory of planned behaviour (TPB)	A theory of planned behaviour is one that connects one's beliefs with behaviour. According to the theory, an individual's behavioural intents and behaviours are shaped by his or her intentions toward behaviour, perceived behavioural, and perceived behavioural control.
Social Cognitive theory	According to social cognition theory, an individual's individuals learn in a social context that involves a and reciprocal relationship of the person, surroundings, and behaviour.
Social Learning Theory (SLT)	Learning theory is an aspect of education and social behaviour theory that suggests that practises can be learned through observation and imitation of others.
Normative theory	The study of moral behavior is known as normative ethics. It is the discipline of moral philosophy that studies the set of concerns that occur while contemplating how one should conduct morally. It aids in ethical decision-making.
Ability Motivation Opportunity (AMO) theory	According to the AMO theory, there are three separate work system factors that shape turned professional and contributes to the organization's success. According to the thesis, a system that considers employees' skill, motivation, and opportunity serves organisational interests best (AMO). The AMO hypothesis has been widely used to describe the intricate relationship between how people are supervised and subsequent performance outcomes.
Social Identity theory (SIT)	The element of an individual's ' self generated from perceived membership of a particular group is referred to as social identity.
New environmental Paradigm (NEP)	It asserts that humans are only one of many creatures on Earth that human behaviors are influenced by environmental as well as social and cultural variables, and that humans are highly dependent on the resources of the environment.
Theory of reasoned model	The idea of reasoned action seeks to explain the interaction of attitudes and behaviours in human activity. It is mostly used to forecast how people will act based on their prior opinions and behavioural intentions.

Qualitative Analysis

The significance of OCBE has increased globally, attracting the interest of numerous researchers and creating a variety of issues for various businesses. The most frequent challenge experienced by the top management is the lack of employee participation in embracing sustainable behavior. This voluntary behavior can only be successful if the perfect match of the employee-organization fit is achieved, otherwise there will be wastage of time and resources of the organizations. The employee organization fit can be achieved by aligning the employee's characteristics with the organization's policies for achieving sustainability (Boiral, Talbot, &Paille, 2015). The study has divided the various antecedents of OCBE into two major categories i.e., Employee level and Organizational level interventions, which are found to impact OCBE positively.

Table 3: Interventions and antecedents for OCBE

Level of intervention	Antecedents	Impact on employees	Relevant studies
Employee leintervention (Employees' individual values)	Altruistic values	These personal characteristics of an individual promote pro-environmental behaviour in the workplace and at home.	Ruepert et. al (2016), Tezel &Giritli, (2019), Blok et. al (2014), Boiral et. al (2013), Raineri&Paille (2015)
	Biospheric values		
	Environmental values and awareness		
	Personal and social norms		
	Individuals' beliefs and green values		
	Attitude		
Spirituality			
Organizational level interventions	Leadership styles - Pro-environment leadership style or the supervisory support for pro-environment behavior	The introduction of environment specific leadership style adopted by management positively impact the employee's green behavior (or OCBE). The introduction and awareness of supervisory support motivates an employee to behave more consciously towards the environment at the workplace.	Ramus & Stege (2000), Paille, Boiral, Chen (2013), Wesselink, Blok, Ringersma (2017), Luu (2018), Robertson & Barling (2013), Blok, Wesselink, Studynka & Kemp (2014), Zhao & Zhou (2019), Anser, Shafique, Usman, Akhtar & Ali (2021), Tuan, Rowley, Masli, Le & Phuong Nhi, (2021).
	HR Strategies (Green HR procedures and practices)	Introducing green HR procedures and practices will lead to increased commitment, financial performance of the organization. Such practices improve the overall organization's image and reputation along with an increase in environmental performance.	Stritch (2014), Tsai & Christensen (2014), Raineri & Paille (2015), Paille, Chen, Boiral & Jin (2014), Alnajdawi Emeagwali & Elrehail (2017), Luu (2018), Gilal, Ashraf, Gilal & Channa (2019), Kim, Choia & Phetvaroon (2019), Paille, Chen, Boiral, Jin, Journal, May & Boirai (2019), Amrutha & Geetha (2020), Yong, Yusliza, Ramayah, Chiappetta Jabbour, Sehnem, & Mani, 2020), Janadari (2021), (Saputro & Nawangsari, 2021), Zhao & Zhou (2021), Zhao, Zhou, He & Jiang (2021).

The table 3 represents the sub categories under the two major levels of interventions which positively impact OCBE in achieving sustainability. These categories are discussed in detail in the next section.

Individual Values and OCBE

Paille et al. (2017) and Gilal&Channa (2019) highlighted the significance of an employee's individual values for improving environmental performance and adopting OCBE within an organization (Olson et. al, 2012). These individual values vary from personality, environmental attitudes, motivation, intention (Norton et. al, 2015), environmental values and awareness, social norms, spirituality, consciousness, (Rezapouraghdam, 2018), and moral reflectiveness contributes to the successful implementation of OCBE within an organization or inculcating green behavior among its employees. Globally, the importance of OCBE has grown, piquing the curiosity of numerous scholars and posing a variety of problems for diverse businesses. Chang (2019) emphasized the importance of shared green vision among employees as an important factor for adopting OCBE and improving performance. The sustainable behavior of employees increases their commitment towards an organization once OCBE is adopted (Kim et al. 2019, (Paille&Meija-Morelos, 2019). Thus, OCBE adoption and long-term sustainability in a company are significantly influenced by the personal values of its personnel (Ojedokun, 2021). The information regarding the individual values of existing and new employees helps an organization make more informed decisions especially pertaining to sustainable behaviors of employees (Paille, Meija-Morelos, Marche-Paille, Chen & Chen, 2016). For example, during the selection process, the beliefs of an individual play an important role in making informed decisions regarding the employee-organization fit. Moreover, the prior knowledge about the individual values of employees will help in predicting the potential hurdles and issues encountered when sustainable behavior is adopted among employees in the organization.

Leadership Styles and OCBE

The vital role played by an organization lies in the environmental specific leadership style (Tuan, 2019; Robertson & Barling, 2013 and Mi et al. 2019) or leader's support (Raineri&Paille, 2015) or manager's role (Wesselink et. al, 2017) or supervisor role (Ramus & Steger, 2000) for implementing OCBE in an organization. The norms of an organization are depicted through an effective leadership style. The motivation intrigued by pro-environment leaders has a long- lasting impact on an employee's behavior (Anser, Shafique, Usman, Akhtar& Ali, 2021, Ramus & Killmer, 2007). The leader's role is of immense importance while introducing an organizational level intervention to obtain an effective result i.e., to embrace OCBE. Researchers have outlined that the effectiveness of OCBE lies in the pro-environment leadership style of an organization (Han, 2019, Tuan, Rowley, Masli, Le & Phuong Nhi, 2021). The environment specific leadership style strengthens the relationship between OCBE and organizational effectiveness (Luu, 2018 and Tuan, 2019). Thus, a leader's role and support are crucial for achieving both OCBE and sustainability (Blok et al, 2014).

HR Strategies and OCBE

For the successful adoption of OCBE, management needs to adopt adequate HR strategies for encouraging its employees to behave sustainably. The introduction of OCBE in organizations has the power to motivate employees and increase retention ratio (Casey and Sieber, 2016, which solves the most critical problem of dissatisfied millennials. The growing importance of OCBE has compelled enterprises to conduct interventions including the adoption of effective HR strategies in the form of Green HR policies that boost the implementation process of OCBE (Raineri & Paille, 2015; Naz, Jamshed, Nisar & Nasir, 2021). (Unsworth et. al, 2013, Silvester, 2019, Janadari, 2021).Yuriev et al. (2018) highlight the challenges encountered in the implementation of OCBE in such a workplace as well as the solutions to these challenges. The introduction of OCBE with the aid of HR tactics like green performance evaluation, green reward and pay, green recruiting and selection, and environmental training and development (Pinzone et al., 2019) contributes to the successful and efficient adoption of OCBE within a business (Silvester et al., 2019, Niyomdech&Yahya, 2019). Further, Salsabiela (2015) emphasized the importance of strategic HRM for inculcating OCBE in an organization. Further, such green interventions contribute to enhanced job satisfaction of employees, motivation and retention ratio (Pinzone et. al, 2019). Thus, in order to implement OCBE successfully and improve environmental performance in an organisation, green HR strategies are essential (Kim et al., 2019; Pinzone et al., 2016, Jayabalan, Makhbul, Mohamed, Yusof&Munir) (2020).

The four HR strategies/green HR policies and practises that directly affect OCBE and sustainability performance are covered in Table 4. Adopting these tactics will improve organisational sustainability performance and OCBE, assisting a company in reaching its sustainability objectives (Saputro&Nawang Sari, 2021).The enhanced commitment of employees to embrace sustainable behavior is the key to achieving the long-term sustainability objective. The adoption of OCBE is still in its evolution stage even though the benefits of such practice are realized by every aspect of the organization. The adoption of such HR strategies for enhanced employee sustainable behavior is important as employees are the biggest asset of an organization.

Table 4: HR strategies (green HR policies and practices)

HR Strategy	Impact	Author(s)
Rewards and recognition	The introduction of green reward and recognition increases employee commitment which leads to the organizational sustainability.	Ramus (2002), Govindarajulu&Daily (2009), Silvester, Sarip&Hassan (2019), Kim, Kim&Choia&Phetvaroon (2019), Niyomdechaa&Yahyab (2019), Amrutha &Geetha (2020), Janadari (2021), (Saputro&Nawangarsi, 2021), Zhao, Zhou, He & Jiang (2021).
Training and development	The introduction of green training and development through education helps employees to take sustainable actions.	Silvester, Sarip& Hassan (2019), Luu (2018), Kim, Kim, Choia&Phetvaroon (2019), Niyomdechaa&Yahyab (2019), Pinzone, Guerci, Lettieri&Huisingh (2019), Amrutha &Geetha (2020), Janadari (2021), (Saputro&Nawangarsi, 2021), Zhao, Zhou, He & Jiang (2021).
Recruitment and selection	The management focusing on green recruitment and selection recognizes that employees must strive for green behavior in order to follow the organization's green policies.	Silvester, Sarip&Hassan (2018), Kim, Kim, Choia&Phetvaroon (2019), Niyomdechaa&Yahyab (2019), Amrutha &Geetha (2020), Janadari (2021), (Saputro&Nawangarsi, 2021), Zhao, Zhou, He & Jiang (2021).
Performance appraisal	The application of green performance appraisal has created an awareness about the importance of an employee's green behavior in the organization leading to sustainability of employees	Niyomdechaa&Yahyab (2019), Silvester, Sarip& Hassan (2019), Amrutha &Geetha (2020), Janadari (2021), (Saputro&Nawangarsi, 2021), Zhao, Zhou, He & Jiang (2021).

The study discussed the various interventions, which positively impact OCBE leading to enhanced organizational performance.

CONCLUSION

Sustainability not only enhances the overall performance of an organization in the long run but also gives a sense of purpose to its employees. The significance of sustainable behavior, or pro-environmental behavior, or OCBE, can be inferred from the year wise distribution, as the number of studies has increased dramatically since 2012 (due to the development of various OCBE measurement scales). The major industries studied for sustainable behavior of employees comprise of 'Tourism & Hospitality', 'Education' and 'Chemical producing industries' which signifies the importance of OCBE in industries that have high environmental footprints (Lu, Zhang, Diao, Liu,Chen, Long& Cai, 2021; Tom&Soumyaja,2019).

With employees being the most crucial factor for an organization to be successful, low employee satisfaction and low retention rate must be resolved. Employees can be motivated to behave in a more sustainable manner using appropriate employee and organizational level interventions. Both the interventions are interdependent. The extent of application of the organizational interventions depends on the individual values of employees such as concern for the environment, their altruistic or environmental values and their beliefs. The initiation of sustainability strategies lies on the part of organizations' initiatives such as HR strategies and environment friendly leadership style (Blok et al., 2014, Tuan 2019, Amrutha & Geetha (2020). The purpose to work for welfare of environment (Chang, 2019) induces happiness of an individual (Rezapouraghdam et al, 2018), leading to more satisfied employees and increasing their commitment. Pinzone et al. (2019) conclude that OCBE has a favourable impact on employment satisfaction and long-term employee behaviour. The increased commitment, happiness, sense of accomplishment and satisfaction among employees have a positive influence on the retention ratio and corporate image of an organization (Corral-Verdugo, Mireles-Acosta, Tapia-Fonllem, & Fraijo-Sing, 2011, Spanjol, Tam & Tam, 2015). The increased environmental awareness has a favourable effect on the organization's environmental performance (Khan, Irshad, Ahmed & Khattak, 2021). As a result, it can be concluded that these benefits of OCBE adoption have a significant positive impact on organisational performance (both financially and environmentally) (Channa, Hussain, Casali, Sarfraz & Dakhan & Aisha, 2021). In order to achieve organisational sustainability throughout time, it is essential to consider both individual values and HR policies and practises (Rezapouraghdam, 2018; Gilal & Channa (2019); Norton et al, 2015; Chang et al, 2019).

In order to embrace OCBE successfully and efficiently, the study examines two levels of interventions, namely employee and organisational, and their sub categories. The literature has studied OCBE in various industries but its common antecedents are still in under study. None of the previous studies focused on the interconnectedness of these two levels of interventions and their positive impact on sustainable behavior. Further, sustainability increases the overall image of an organization, increases its green performance and makes it more profitable (Casey and Sieber, 2016; Chang, 2019; Silvester, 2019). It can be inferred that it is of immense importance for organizations to achieve sustainability in order to accomplish long term goals and they must start the process now before it's too late by embracing OCBE.

FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

The need for organisations sustainability in the long run arises the need for OCBE within every organization. The organizational factors such as environment friendly leadership style and attitude (Tuan, 2019), communication of environmental policies (Raineri and Paille, 2015), green shared culture and vision (Chang et al., 2019), adoption of the environment management system (Darnall et al., 2008), are unfathomed for embracing sustainable behavior in an organization, which can be considered by future researchers for comprehensive study. Future research could focus on other factors like corporate social responsibility (Malik et al., 2021) and environment management policies which can be empirically examined under the organizational level initiatives for implementing OCBE (Cheema, Afsar & Javed, 2020). To

figure out how that these personal attributes are applicable to organisational sustainable strategies, researchers can instead look at some other aspects of one's characteristics including environmental concern, personality, and environmental values. The applicability of OCBE in various industries is still unexplored oil and gas, and pharmaceuticals which have huge waste disposal issues. In addition, the measurement scales developed have few drawbacks with respect to applicability in various industries, which raises the need for a more inclusive scale that has increased relevance. In the future, researchers may examine the empirical connections between the two levels of interventions and their sub categories for an in-depth understanding of the antecedents of OCBE that can be applied to any organization irrespective of its size.

The researcher can study the scope of the OCBE implementation process by including the key variables for OCBE such as affective organizational commitment, social norms, environmental awareness at the employee level and pro-environment motivation, green shared values, green climate, green culture at the organizational level for further studies (Zientara & Zamojska, 2018). The researchers can include the organizational climate and culture in fostering organizational sustainability. The adoption of the environment friendly management system into an organization could be one of the additional HR strategies that need to be analyzed. Researchers can empirically test the various interventions discussed across industries and the globe. The empirical testing of OCBE's impact on high waste generating industries such as IT, FMCG, manufacturing, hospitality and pharmaceutical industry is recommended for future studies (Milanesi, Runfola & Guercini, 2020).

Implications

Sustainability is a management strategy that focuses on how a certain firm functions in the ecological, social, and economic environments in order to create long-term value. The study suggests that aligning employees' vision with that of the organization may enhance their commitment (Paille et al. 2017) and satisfaction (Lamm et al. 2014); a growing concern for corporates. The goal of achieving sustainability in an organization through employees' sustainable behavior can be achieved through the adoption of OCBE. Implementing sustainability and OCBE improves an organization's environmental effectiveness, which benefits all stockholders, including its landholders (shareholders), workers, stock holders, customers, board of directors, and so on, but most pertinently, the surroundings in which a company's internal control (Paille et al., 2018; Han et al., 2019; Tuan, 2019). As a result, the process of becoming more sustainable through OCBE will make the organisation more profitable in the long run (Tuan, 2019).

For effective implementation, managers must consider the pivotal role of employees in adopting OCBE within an organization and achieving sustainability (Boirall & Paille, 2012 and Daily et al., 2009). The millennial workforce is particularly responsive to this sustainable behaviour, as Steele (2019) noted that 70% of generation y employees are more inclined to accept a job at a company that supports the environment. This signify that individuals' values of an employee are vital for achieving sustainability (Gilal & Channa (2019). For instance, at the time of recruitment, people with strong environmental beliefs or values must be given

priority which will eventually lead to more efficient implementation of OCBE and achieving organizational sustainability in the long run. Apart from employees, organizational level interventions determine the success and effectiveness of organizational sustainability, such as pro-environment leadership style (Mi et al. 2019, Paille et al., 2017) and HR strategies (Anwar et al. 2020). The intensity of these interventions may vary from organization to organization depending upon its characteristics and ethics. Thus, management must scrutinise interventions that foster employees' participation in such sustainable activities and adopt HR strategies that align the goal of a sustainable organization with that of the sustainable behaviour of employees.

LIMITATIONS

The study has few limitations. First, papers are collected from only two databases, which narrowed down the search. The researchers can include other databases for obtaining wider search like Scopus, Academia and Science Direct. Second, the study limits its reach by covering articles published between 2000 and 2022 only. Third, future researchers can include remaining key variables such as employee's attitude, organizational culture and climate which are not included in the study for more exhaustive research. Fourth, study undertakes the integrative analysis of OCBE containing only the descriptive analysis and antecedents of OCBE. The future researchers may include the mediators and moderators for OCBE and their impact in obtaining organizational sustainability.

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